

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-04

Treated municipal
wastewater reuse for
enhanced irrigation
resilience

//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Reuse of treated municipal wastewater for irrigation, on-site tertiary treatment step (e.g. ultraviolet disinfection)

INPUTS

Treated municipal wastewater (effluent from at least secondary treatment)

OUTPUTS

Disinfected high quality irrigation water

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 7

CONTEXT & SCALE

Farm-level application for agriculture in water-scarce regions where treated municipal wastewater is available, and appropriate storage or piping infrastructure, and disinfection can be ensured

KEY BENEFITS

Reduced freshwater demand; continuous water supply; improved resilience to droughts including more stable yields; potential reduction in synthetic fertilizer use

MAIN CONSTRAINTS

Tertiary treatment (e.g. ultraviolet disinfection) required; on-farm water storage tanks or a piped connection to the WWTP required; monitoring for quality control and regulatory compliance

CATEGORY

Wastewater and Biowaste Recycling

//02. WHAT IT IS

Treated municipal wastewater (at least secondary treatment) is used as an alternative water source for crop irrigation. If there are no connection pipe network from the wastewater treatment plant to the farm, it integrates appropriate on-farm storage, and conveyance with a tertiary treatment step (e.g. ultraviolet disinfection) to en-

sure hygienic safety (in line with minimum requirements for water reuse in EU Regulation 2020/741). Where required, treated wastewater can also be blended with other available water sources, like groundwater or rainwater, to adjust nutrient concentrations or salinity and optimise irrigation management.

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//03. WHY IT MATTERS

In water-scarce regions, increasingly frequent and prolonged dry periods threaten agricultural production, particularly water-demanding crops like fruit orchards (e.g., citrus orchards), and traditionally rainfed cultivations such as olive groves and vineyards, where freshwater for irriga-

tion is limited. Reusing treated municipal wastewater provides a continuous alternative water source, reduces dependence on scarce freshwater resources and supports a transition to more climate-resilient irrigation, while also offering a source of valuable nutrients and trace minerals.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

This solution comprises storage, treatment, and conveyance components that enable the safe reuse of treated municipal wastewater (at least secondary treatment) for agricultural irrigation. Wastewater can be supplied either via a direct connection to the wastewater treatment plant or through tanker delivery. On-site storage and/or conveyance infrastructure allows to buffer supply variability and support controlled irrigation scheduling. Final hygienic safety is ensured through a tertiary treatment step for polishing and disinfection (e.g. ultraviolet disinfection); depending

on source water quality, additional filtration may be required to manage turbidity. System configuration and sizing reflect local conditions, including crop type and irrigation demand, water availability and supply modality, field layout and hydraulic constraints, water quality characteristics, and applicable regulatory and monitoring requirements. Depending on crop type and the targeted water reuse class, different irrigation systems may be applied (e.g. drip irrigation, subsurface drip irrigation, and low-pressure micro- or mini-sprinkler systems).

Wastewater Treatment Plant

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//05. HOW IT WORKS

Depending on site-specific conditions, the wastewater transported to a site may be stored in covered or underground tanks to buffer supply variability and enable scheduled irrigation. Prior to irrigation use, the treated effluent undergoes a tertiary disinfection step (e.g. ultraviolet disinfection), which may be implemented in-line or within storage units. Monitoring and control

systems (e.g. disinfection status, flow and pressure, and water quality checks) support safe operation and compliance with applicable reuse requirements. Where appropriate, prior to irrigation, treated effluent may be blended with groundwater or other suitable water sources for agronomic optimisation, including the adjustment of nutrient concentrations and salinity.

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

Operation and maintenance focus on ensuring safe water reuse and a reliable irrigation supply. This includes management of water supply logistics (e.g. tank filling levels and delivery schedules) and regular inspection of storage units and conveyance infrastructure.

The tertiary disinfection system is subject to routine inspection and cleaning in accordance with manufacturer specifications to ensure consistent performance. Regular water quality sampling confirms irrigation suitability and compliance with hygienic safety requirements.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

Key risks include potential health and hygienic risks in case of water quality fluctuation or insufficient disinfection, and supply interruptions where water delivery relies on tanker transport. These risks are effectively mitigated through appropriate system design, with particular emphasis

on the tertiary treatment process, regular inspection, and maintenance verifying the performance of the disinfection step. Continuous monitoring supports safe water reuse in compliance with minimum requirements for water reuse in EU Regulation 2020/741.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

Reuse of treated wastewater is a good fit in water-scarce regions for water-demanding crops like fruit orchards (e.g., citrus orchards) and farms transitioning from rainfed cultivation to irrigation and have access to treated municipal wastewater. It is particularly suitable where drip irrigation system is/can be installed and where the necessary infrastructure and procedures for safe reuse through secure storage, dis-

infection, and regular monitoring can be put in place.

In the GEORGIA project, reuse of municipal treated wastewater for irrigation is implemented on [traditional vineyards of Santorini Island, Greece](#), on olive groves and citrus orchards in [Korinthos, Greece](#), and citrus orchards at [Phassouri Plantations, in Limassol, Cyprus](#).

//09. KEYWORDS

Treated wastewater reuse; Municipal effluent; Drip irrigation; Alternative water sources; Drought resilience

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

//10. REFERENCES

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//11. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

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